

Cathodic Protection of Underground Mild Steel Pipes by Impressed Current using Solar Cells as Rectifier

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ABSTRACT

The need for constant supply of electricity to protect steel structures brings about the use of solar cells. This research work involves the cathodic protection of underground mild steel pipes by impressed current using solar cells as rectifier. The pipes were buried at two separate sites; X and Y. Site X for the control experiment and Y for the main experiment. The Impressed Current cathodic Protection (ICCP) was applied to the pipes on site Y and the pipes on site X buried without any protection for a period of 40 days. The Pipe to Soil Potentials (PSP) was measured for the pipes on the two sites using multimeter. The pipe to soil potentials measured for the pipes on site Y were within the range recommended for protection ($<-850\text{mV}$) and that of the pipes on site X were above the range. Protection efficiencies using the results obtained from the PSP tests were obtained with maximum protection efficiencies of 82%. Physical examination and microstructures of the pipes also indicated visible proof of corrosion on the buried pipes without protection and this was not seen on the buried pipes under ICCP using solar cell.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mild steel is one of the most commonly used forms of steel with a wide range of desirable properties such as low tensile strength, ductility, strength, toughness, and machinability among others. Consequently, it finds application in industries such as in the production of automotive, oil and gas, and construction amongst others (Adetoro, 2013). It is also known as low carbon steel, relatively available and cost less to produce. Non-noble metals of this kind and their alloys are employed as materials for installation of pipelines, reservoirs and underground storage vessels (Mujezinovic and Turkonovic, 2017). However, the excellent properties possessed by

this form of steel do not include resistance to corrosion as stated by Chinwko *et al.*, 2014. Corrosion leads to loss in steel structures cross-sectional area, eventual collapse and reduction in service life (Lambert *et al.*, 2015). The process of corrosion is an electrochemical reaction which occurs when the metal reacts with the environment and most times, results in the deterioration of the material and loss of products (Loto and Popoola, 2011). The consequences of corrosion are as revealed in the 2001 Motiva petrol refinery facility failure in the USA (Omotosho *et al.*, 2018). It can result in dangerous, irreversible and expensive damage to every materials structure made of steel i.e pipelines, bridges and public buildings, vehicles, water and wastewater systems, it is one of the most serious problems in the industry especially the oil and gas (Okewale and Olaitan, 2017). Oil field water containing substances of sodium chloride, hydrogen sulphide, carbon-dioxide and oxygen tend to increase corrosion rate of oil pipelines leading to eventual failure (Unueroh *et al.*, 2016). Direct and indirect economic losses associated with corrosion include costs of replacing corroded structures and loss of product respectively (Abdullatef, 2017). Study conducted by US Department of Transportation showed that pipeline corrosion incidents alone accounts for about a quarter of total incidents at an economic cost of over 160 million dollars (Ee and Aziz, 2018). **A hybrid prediction model was developed for pipeline corrosion using artificial neural network with particle swarm optimization.**

The corrosion process requires the presence of four components namely; the anode, cathode, electrolyte and a metallic path (Marwah *et al.*, 2014). Corrosion occurs by electrons transfer from the anode to the cathode, the anode oxidizes while the cathode is reduced as it is with any form of electrochemical cell. The resulting effect is the degradation of the anodic site (Chinwko *et al.*, 2014). There are several methods by which corrosion can be prevented one of which is the Cathodic Protection (CP). This method simply prevents corrosion by making the structure meant for protection cathodic in the supposed corrosion cell according to Laoun *et al.*, 2009. Essentially, CP predetermines the anode in the corrosion cell, or making a large corrosion cell to overcome the other smaller corrosion cells (Guyer, 2014). This is done by forcing an electric current to flow through the electrolyte towards the surface of the metal required to be protected (Marwah *et al.*, 2014). The methods by which cathodic protection is carried out are galvanic anode (sacrificial anode), impressed current and biological cathodic protection (Ali *et al.*, 2018). Galvanic anode method involves the attachment of another metal which is more active. When the more active metal is attached, it supplies the current required in the corrosion cell and thus corrodes in place of the material to be protected, it is also known as the sacrificial anode cathodic protection method (Guyer, 2014). The metals are in most time alloyed to improve on their dissolution behaviors (Byrne *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, the work conducted by Ding *et al.* (2018) showed that AC interference is notable in the corrosion of magnesium alloy sacrificial anode. Hosokawa *et al.* (2004) mitigated this using new CP criterion by distributed magnesium anodes method. In cases where the current required for protection is high and not attainable by the galvanic anode method, the impressed current method is employed. **Thus ICCP system has an edge in this situation considering its efficiency and cost saving in term of replacing consumed anodes.**

The ICCP system applies a source of Direct Current (DC) that forces the current to flow from an installed anode(s) to the structure, causing the entire structure to be a cathode. The electrical current continuously regulated and monitored by the ICCP system prevents the electrochemical mechanism of galvanic corrosion prior to its attack as reported by Michopoulos *et al.*, 2018. A

rectifier, solar cell, battery, generator, or some other DC power supply is installed in the circuit. The selection of anode material is free from the galvanic series considerations and anodes are chosen which are economical, or metals which have a small weight loss per ampere year of current. Impressed-current systems employ inert (zero or low dissolution) anodes and use an external source of dc power to impress a current from an external anode onto the cathode surface (American Bureau of Shipping, 2017). Stray current corrosion of underground structures may result when ICCP rectifiers are connected backwards, though in rare cases, in a manner that the DC current discharges from the structure while the anode rather collects (Kolawole *et al.*, 2018). Several studies on ICCP have been conducted which considered factors such as anode distance and depth, wet and dry soil resistivity, coated and uncoated pipe conditions and the required current amount and distribution for steel pipes protection (Harbi *et al.*, 2017). The work of Chen *et al.* (2018) showed that cathodic protection and hydrogen evolution potentials of X100 steel examined under three soil samples from different locations are largely dependent on the pH of the respective soil. Besides, electrical resistivity of the soil environment is another very important fact for a cathodic protection system (Janowski and Wantuch, 2016). Resistivity decrease, temperature increase and aeration flow rate increase of solution environment causes increase in corrosion rate of pipe which consequently leads to increase in cathodic protection current requirement for ICCP system (Abdul-Sada *et al.*, 2016). Hashim *et al.* (2014) in their study observed that temperature had most effect on ICCP system as an increase in its value reduced oxygen solubility and diffusion rate and a subsequent drop in corrosion rate, followed by concentration then aeration. It is evident in the study by El-Alem *et al.* (2013) that increase in pipeline diameter and length results in increase in the number of required anodes. **This makes the use of sacrificial anode cathodic protection costly.**

Availability of electric power may not often be possible, high cost of replacing used sacrificial anodes coupled with the need to protect portable equipment like ocean liners necessitate the deployment of ICCP system with solar rectifier. Khan *et al.* (2018) found that the solar PV system as DC source supplied more constant DC power to ICCP system in hot and cold weather conditions and high and low resistivity environments compared to thermoelectric generator and transformer rectifier. CP causes no debonding between coating and steel substrate but rather decelerates degradation process of coating and delays electrochemical reactions at the steel-electrolyte interface (Fan *et al.*, 2018). Marginal polarization of pipelines is ensured by supplying voltage which does not fall below requirement, maintaining constant flow of current to structure above demand current of environment (Ameh and Ikpeseni, 2017). A power storage system of batteries would help ensure the cathodic protection is available all day even when the sun is not out. The need for constant supply of electricity to protect steel structures brings about the use of solar cells. This study therefore **aimed to investigate** the use of solar cells as the source of DC current to power cathodic protection system using impressed current for buried mild steel pipes. **The experimental set up would be conducted, pipe to soil potentials would be measured regularly for protected and unprotected buried pipes and efficiency determined.**

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials, tools and equipment used for the CP of mild steel by impressed current are mild steel pipes, anode **made of steel plate**, copper-copper sulfate (Cu-CuSO_4) reference electrode, electrical connectors (wire), 18V solar module/panel, charge controller, 12V deep cycle battery, digital multi-meter **of medium capacity**, pickaxe, measuring tape, pH meter. Materials used for

the development of the reference electrode are copper electrode, copper sulfate (CuSO_4) salt, porous stopper (foam), **digital weighing scale**, distilled water and transparent tube.

2.1 Site Preparation

Two sites labelled X and Y were selected for the experiment. Site X for the control i.e. pipes buried without CP and site Y for the main experiment i.e. pipes buried under CP applied. Each site contained three trenches of 0.25m depth, 1m long and 0.090m wide. The trenches were dug 0.10m apart. The entire site(s) for the experiments was marked for recognition and to avoid trespassing. Soil samples of the sites were taken, and the pH value was measured and recorded using a pH meter. **The method used by Khan et al., 2018 was adopted.**

2.2 Pipes Preparation

Six pipes with dimensions of **1 m** length, 75 mm diameter and 2mm thickness were used for the experiments (3 pipes for each site). The pipes were cleaned with an emery cloth and the weights of the pipes were measured before the experiment using a digital weighing scale. The pipes were labeled A, B and C for the unprotected and D, E and F for the protected buried at depth 25 cm and 10 cm apart in sites X and Y respectively. Each pipe was then wound with a 15 cm copper wire to facilitate the measurement of the pipe to soil potential of the buried pipes.

2.3 Installation of Solar Module and Electrical Setup

The solar module was mounted on the roof of a building at site Y with the aid of electrical cables (DC cables). The solar module output was connected to the input of the charge controller for which its output was connected to the battery terminals with consideration of polarity for the continuous charging of the battery. The positive and negative terminals of the battery were then connected with copper cables to the anode and pipes respectively via series connection.

2.4 Fabrication of Reference Electrode

The reference electrode used was the copper-copper sulfate (Cu-CuSO_4) reference electrode (Figure 1). Due to its unavailability in the local market and difficulty in acquiring it from the foreign market, the electrode was developed in-country. The ends of the tube were made open with one end of the tube fitted with the porous stopper and the other with the copper rod attached to the cover. A saturated solution of copper sulfate salts was prepared with 25 ml of distilled water. It was ensured that excess copper sulfate salts were contained in the solution.

Figure 1 Schematic Copper-Copper Sulfate reference electrode

2.5 Pipe to Soil Potentials Measurement

Three points (I, II, III) along the pipes' length were marked as points of contact for the reference electrode. The negative probe of the digital multimeter was connected to the cable protruding from the buried pipe while the positive probe was connected to the reference electrode. The reference electrode was made to contact the soil at points I, II and III and the voltage readings recorded. The site was constantly wetted to ensure good contact of the reference electrode with the soil. This was done to also make the soil a good electrolyte as the soil was relatively dry at normal times. Set-up for ICCP using solar cell is as shown in Figure 2. The efficiencies of protection for the protected pipe at site Y was obtained based on Equation 1.

$$Z = \frac{V_1 - V_2}{V_1} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where Z= protection efficiency; V_1 = mean potential after protection; V_2 = potential difference before protection (415.78 mV)

Figure 2 Schematic of the Impressed Current Cathodic Protection Set-Up

3. RESULTS

3.1 Pipe to Soil Potentials (PSP) and Protection Efficiency

The results of the average PSP measured for each site and the efficiencies of protection obtained per days are as shown in Table 1 and Figure 3.

Table 1 Average PSP for sites X and Y and Protection Efficiency using Solar Cell as Rectifier

Days	PSP at Site X (mV)	PSP at Site Y (mV)	Efficiency %
1	304.4444	1233.111	66
2	281.2222	1087.333	62
5	235.1111	654.2222	36
7	243.1111	631.2222	34
8	255.5555	1459.000	72
9	265.6667	1370.111	70
14	234.7778	1377.667	70
30	127.6667	918.4445	55
33	157.7778	1049.556	60
35	150.2222	745.8889	44
37	103.3333	2255.333	82

40 104.3333 1586.126 74

Figure 3 Average PSP Values for Sites X and Y using Solar Cell as Rectifier

3.2 Physical Inspection

Macro examination of the buried steel pipes after exhuming revealed near-nature of the as-received form for the ICCP protected pipes and corrosion of unprotected ones as pictured in Figure 4a and b respectively.

Figure 4 Exhumed (a) Pipes from site Y (b) Pipes from site X

3.3 Microstructure Test Results

Figures 5 and 6 show the surface morphology taken of samples cut out from the pipes. The samples were examined after the experiment using a metallurgical microscope with a magnification of x200 in order to observe the photographic composition of the samples cut out from the pipes buried with and without protection.

Figure 5 Photomicrograph of Pipe Samples from Site Y using Solar Cell as Rectifier

Figure 6 Photomicrograph of Pipe Samples from Site X using Solar Cell as Rectifier

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

One of the criteria for protection is a voltage of -0.85 mV relative to a saturated copper/copper sulfate electrode for underground steel structures (NACE; Fu, 2012). Thus, it can be deduced that the pipes on site Y corroded less as a result of the protection applied while site X pipes corroded more for lack of protection. The PSP values of the pipes at site X measured above -850 mV, thus corrosion occurred in the pipes. PSP values measured at site Y were below -850 mV for both set ups, which satisfy the criteria for cathodic protection. All PSP values obtained were not below -2000 mV which indicated absence of over-protection on the mild steel pipes in the set ups thus guaranteed non-generation of hydrogen gas.

Physical appearances of the pipes after they were exhumed showed a substantial rate of corrosion on the buried pipes without protection while the buried ones with impressed current cathodic protection looked very closely to their as-received forms.

Maximum cathodic protection efficiency of 82% obtained from ICCP using solar cell as rectifier is greater than 22% inhibitive efficiency obtained using kerosene as inhibitor on mild steel in HCl environment from an earlier work (Adetunji *et al.*, 2017).

5. CONCLUSION

Sequel to the results obtained from this work, the following are conclusions drawn:

- ❖ Solar cells are efficient for the application of impressed current CP as the pipes buried without protection experienced corrosion and the pipes buried with impressed current cathodic protection did not experience corrosion relatively.
- ❖ The efficiency of the cathodic protection was at an average of 64.2% and can be improved upon by organic coating of the pipes.

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NOMENCLATURE

Z= protection efficiency

V_1 = mean potential after protection

V_2 = potential difference before protection